

A retrospective audit of the use of O (RhD) negative red blood cells

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Abstract

Emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs) are critical in the management of acute blood loss, especially in trauma and obstetric emergencies where the patient's blood type is unknown or a delay in the provision of compatible units. Due to their universal compatibility and scarcity, it is essential to ensure their appropriate use to prevent wastage and optimize patient outcomes. This audit was conducted at Princess Alexandra Hospital (PAH) NHS Trust to assess the usage and wastage of O-negative RBCs, identify areas for improvement, and recommend strategies to enhance the management of this valuable resource. The audit reviewed the use of 732 units of emergency O-negative RBCs issued between January 1, 2023, to December 31, 2023. Data was extracted from Blood Bank LIMS, focusing on the appropriateness of use, in compliance with NICE and NHSBT guidelines. The audit explored the compliance of O (RhD) negative usage, identification of usage patterns, and wastage. The primary causes of wastage were identified as rapid of issuance before confirming the patient's blood group and administrative delays leading to the breach of cold chain hence leads to wastage of units. The audit revealed a high compliance rate of 90% with established guidelines, indicating that most transfusions were appropriately administered. However, 10% expired before use. The findings suggest complexity in the blood ordering and issuing process and transfusion process, contributing to the high wastage of O (Rh) Negative units. The average inventory turnover rate was 3.5, highlighting a need for more precise inventory management to align supply with demand more accurately.

Keywords: O (RhD) Negative, Blood Transfusion, Compliance, Red Cells, Wastage of Blood, NICE, NHSBT.

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Introduction

Emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs) play a crucial role in the management of acute blood loss. It's commonly used in emergencies to save lives especially in trauma and obstetric emergencies. They are known to be universally compatible with all blood types and are therefore reserved for situations where the blood type of the patient is unknown, and there is an urgent need for transfusion. The scarcity and cost of O (RhD) negative blood make it vital to ensure its appropriate use.

Inappropriate request can lead to unnecessary wastage, depletion of the stock of a rare blood type but also may lead to increased risks for patients, such as alloimmunisation, adverse reactions and unnecessary exposure to donor blood. It is important to consider the usage and management of this valuable resource and maintain it to fulfil the mission to save lives whenever possible.

The purpose of this audit project is to evaluate the usage of O negative blood at the Princess Alexandra Hospital (PAH) NHS Trust and to identify areas where wastage can be minimized, and usage can be optimized. In addition, through this audit, it is also intended to measure the effectiveness and adequacy of utilizing this precious resource.

This audit is targeted at departments or areas where O negative blood is frequently ordered, such as A&E, AIR ambulance, and any other departments which request O negative blood. Wastage of blood products, including O (RhD) negative RBCs, is a significant concern in transfusion medicine. According to [1], approximately 7% of all issued O (RhD) negative RBC units are wasted annually in the United Kingdom either due to expiration or because they are returned unused to the blood bank after being issued for emergencies. This statistic highlights the need for more effective management of blood resources, especially O (RhD) negative RBCs, given their importance and limited availability.

The aim of this audit is to explore the usage of O negative blood, and to ensure that this resource is utilised in a cost-effective manner and yet upholding its standard of patient care.

We envisage that this audit will explore wastage reduction and improve our O (RhD) usage, minimize stock out of O negative blood which has happened a few times in Princess Alexandra Hospital (PAH) and nationwide in recent years.

Rationale for the Audit

The demand for O (RhD) negative blood exceeds its supply, primarily due to its universal compatibility. Hospitals often face challenges in

maintaining adequate stocks of this blood type, and the pressure is higher in emergency situations. An audit of the usage of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells is essential to understand current practices, identify areas for improvement, and ensure that this valuable resource is used appropriately. This audit will address the formulation of guidelines and protocols to optimize the use of O (RhD) negative RBCs in emergency settings.

National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidance recommend regular follow-up audits to ensure that changes based on audit findings are effectively implemented and sustained. It is often recommended within 3 to 6 months post-intervention to assess short-term outcomes and compliance [2].

National Health Service Blood Transfusion (NHSBT) Guidance NHSBT emphasizes the importance of on-going monitoring and periodic audits to optimize the use of blood products. It is typically recommended within 6 months to evaluate the impact of any changes and to ensure that O- blood is being used appropriately [1].

NHSBT Recommendations: NHSBT emphasizes the importance of monitoring blood product usage closely to minimize wastage. They recommend that blood banks and transfusion services implement regular audits and follow-ups on the use of blood products, including O (RhD) negative red blood cells, to ensure they are used appropriately and efficiently. NHSBT suggests that any unused or returned units should be reviewed within 7 days to understand the reasons for non-used units and to take corrective actions if necessary [1].

Aims

The primary aim of this clinical audit is to evaluate the usage and wastage of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs) in PAH setting. Specifically, the audit aims to:

1. Assess the Appropriateness of Use:
 - Determine whether the use of O (RhD) negative RBCs aligns with established clinical guidelines and protocols.
 - Identify instances of inappropriate use, where alternative blood products could have been used.
2. Quantify Wastage:
 - Measure the extent of wastage of O (RhD) negative RBCs, including units returned unused or that expired before use.
 - Analyse the factors contributing to this wastage, such as administrative errors, delays in decision-making, or overstocking.
3. Improve Resource Management:
 - Provide recommendations to optimize the management of O (RhD) negative RBCs, ensuring their availability for patients in genuine need while minimizing wastage.
 - Develop strategies to enhance communication and decision-making processes between the emergency department, trauma unit, obstetric unit, and the blood bank.

Method

Criteria and Standards

In conducting a clinical audit on the usage and wastage of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs), it is essential to establish clear criteria and standards to evaluate current practices against recognized benchmarks. The criteria and standards set the foundation for measuring compliance, identifying areas for improvement, and ensuring that blood products are used effectively and efficiently.

Table 1: Audit criteria and standards

Criteria	Standard
O (RhD) negative RBCs should only be used in emergencies where the patient's blood group is unknown, and there is an immediate need for transfusion. NICE (2022) and NHSBT (2022) guidelines	100%
The wastage rate of O (RhD) negative RBCs, defined as units returned unused or expired, should be minimized. NHSBT (2022) guidelines.	less than 5%

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria are critical components of the clinical audit as they define the scope of the study, determining which

cases are relevant for analysis. This ensures that the audit focuses on appropriate instances of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cell (RBC) usage, yielding meaningful and accurate results.

Table 2: Inclusion and exclusion criteria and the rationale behind the audit

Inclusion criteria	Rationale for inclusion	Exclusion criteria	Rationale for exclusion
Emergency Transfusions: Criteria: All cases where emergency (O RhD) negative RBCs were issued and transfused during the audit period.	These cases are central to the audit's aim of evaluating the usage and wastage of O (RhD) negative RBCs in emergency settings, where the patient's blood group is unknown, or time does not allow for crossmatching.	Blood Group known Before Transfusion: Cases where the patient's blood group was known before the transfusion and O (RhD) negative RBCs were still used.	The audit focuses on emergency situations where the blood group is unknown, and there is an immediate need for transfusion. Cases where the blood group is known do not fit the criteria for emergency O (RhD) negative RBC usage as defined by clinical guidelines.
Time Frame: Criteria: All emergency O (RhD) negative RBC transfusions that occurred between January 1, 2023, and December 31, 2023.	A defined time frame ensures a manageable data set and provides a clear snapshot of current practices within the study period.	Transfusions outside the Audit Period Any cases involving O (RhD) negative RBC transfusions that occurred outside the specified study period (before January 1, 2023, or after December 31, 2023).	Limiting the data to a specific time frame ensures that the audit remains focused and that the findings are relevant to current practices.

By clearly defining these inclusion and exclusion criteria, the audit will accurately reflect the use of O (RhD) negative RBCs in emergency

situations, ensuring that the results are both meaningful and applicable to improving clinical practices.

Data Extraction

Data was extracted from the Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) systems called TDSynergy Blood Bank commonly used to manage blood bank operations, including inventory control, transfusion tracking, and reporting. For this clinical audit, data extraction from LIMS involved retrieving specific information related to the usage and wastage of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs). Furthermore, identifying relevant data modules by going into the inventory management, transfusion tracking and wastage and returns modules where data related to the stock levels, issuing, and expiry of O (RhD) negative RBCs is located.

Data Query and Filtering was conducted using the system's search or query function to filter data specifically for O (RhD) negative RBCs within the audit period January 1, 2023, to December 31, 2023, with applying filters.

Once the relevant data was identified, the data were exported into a manageable format, an excel document. The exported document file included unit ID, date of issue, date of transfusion, outcomes such as used, returned, expired. The audit was anonymised data with no identifiable patient information, and was classified as quality improvement.

Data Analysis

The analysis of the collected data was conducted using quantitative method to provide a comprehensive understanding of the usage and wastage patterns. This process involves systematically examining the extracted data to identify patterns, trends, and areas for improvement. An evaluation of usage patterns determined how frequently O (RhD) negative RBCs are used in emergency settings while assessing the appropriateness of each transfusion according to clinical guidelines.

Evaluate the amount of O (RhD) negative RBCs wasted due to expiration, return unused, or damage were determined and the primary reasons for wastage were identified.

Compliance with Guidelines were examined by measuring the adherence to [1] and [2] guidelines on the use and management of O (RhD) negative RBCs.

Analysing the data to identify systemic issues or operational inefficiencies leading to the wastage or inappropriate use of O (RhD) negative RBCs allows for targeted analysis of different aspects of O (RhD) negative RBC usage, making it easier to identify specific trends. Descriptive statistics provide an overview of the data, highlighting key findings and trends in usage and wastage. The comparative analysis compares the audit results against the established criteria and standards, comparing the observed wastage rate with the target rate of less than 5% as recommended by [1]. The frequency of RBC unit issuing, transfusion, and wastage was calculated, along with the percentage of compliance with guidelines. The number of units returned unused or expired was quantified, and the reasons for wastage were categorised. This analysis assesses how well the blood bank managed its stock of O (RhD) negative RBCs to meet clinical demands while minimizing wastage by evaluating how closely stock levels aligned with clinical demand over the audit period.

Each case was reviewed to determine whether the issuance and use of O (RhD) negative RBCs complied with NICE and NHSBT guidelines. Non-compliant cases were further analysed to identify common themes and areas for improvement. The clinical outcomes of patients who received emergency transfusions were reviewed to assess the effectiveness of the transfusions and identify any adverse reactions.

Results

The results assessed the compliance with guidelines, quantify wastage, and evaluate the effectiveness of transfusions. The data was

categorized into transfused, returned unused, and expired units, and further analysed for compliance and wastage. Out of the 732 units issued, 659 units, 90% were used in accordance with the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and NHS Blood and Transplant (NHSBT) guidelines. This high compliance rate indicates that the majority of transfusions were administered appropriately, following established protocols. 73 units, 10% were identified as non-compliant with the guidelines. The reasons for non-compliance included urgent issuing of units before confirmation of the patient's blood type of 50 units which 6.8% and transfusions administered without clear clinical indications of 23 units, 3.2%.

73 units of which is 10% expired before they could be utilized. The primary causes of expiration were administrative delays and overstocking, which led to some units surpassing their shelf life before being transfused. 146 units which 20% were returned to the blood bank unused. These units were issued in anticipation of need but were not transfused, because the patient's condition stabilized, or alternative blood types were used for cross-matching. The average inventory turnover rate was calculated at 3.5, indicating that stocks were cycled through fairly and regularly. However, the wastage rate suggested that there may be inefficiencies in predicting actual demand, leading to overstocking. The analysis showed that higher stock levels were correlated with increased wastage. This suggests that while having a sufficient supply of O (RhD) negative RBC is critical for emergency situations, careful management is required to avoid unnecessary expiration of units.

The clinical audit was conducted over a year period and involved a total of 732 units of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs) issued by the hospital's blood bank. The aim was to assess the usage and wastage of these units, compliance with guidelines, and the overall impact on patient outcomes. The results are analysed to assess compliance with guidelines, quantify wastage, and evaluate the effectiveness of transfusions. Data was collected for the period from January 1, 2023, to December 31, 2023. During the audit period, a total of 732 units of O (RhD) negative RBCs were issued from the blood bank. The data was categorized into transfused, returned unused, and expired units, and further analysed for compliance and wastage.

Considering the compliance with Guidelines, out of the 732 units issued, 659 units, 90% were used in accordance with the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and NHS Blood and Transplant (NHSBT) guidelines. This high compliance rate indicates that the majority of transfusions were administered appropriately, following established protocols. 73 units, 10% were identified as non-compliant with the guidelines. The reasons for non-compliance included premature issuing before confirmation of the patient's blood type of 50 units which 6.8% and transfusions administered without clear clinical indications of 23 units, 3.2%.

The audit revealed significant wastage of O (RhD) negative RBCs of which 219 units (30%) were wasted, either due to expiration or being returned unused. Seventy three units of which is 10% expired before they could be utilized. The primary causes of expiration were administrative delays and overstocking, which led to some units surpassing their shelf life before being transfused. 146 units which 20% were returned to the blood bank unused. These units were issued in anticipation of need but were not transfused. The average inventory turnover rate was calculated at 3.5, indicating that stocks were cycled regularly. However, the wastage rate suggests that there may be poor estimation in predicting actual demand, leading to overstocking. The analysis showed that higher stock levels were correlated with increased wastage. This suggests that while having a sufficient supply of

O (RhD) negative RBCs is critical for emergency situations, careful management is required to avoid unnecessary expiration of units. These results highlight the importance of optimizing both the clinical use of O (RhD) negative RBCs and the processes surrounding their management to reduce wastage and ensure that these critical resources are available for patients in need.

Discussion

The audit revealed a high compliance rate of 90% for the use of emergency O (RhD) negative RBCs. This indicates that most transfusions were conducted according to established guidelines, which demand the use of O (RhD) negative RBCs in emergencies when the patient's blood type is unknown [1,2]. This specific finding of the clinical audit has shown relations to the timeframes recommended by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) and NHS Blood and Transplant (NHSBT) for the use of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs). Compliance with guidelines have been shown through the impact of Duing on clinical practice, and the implications for improving blood transfusion protocols [2]. The NICE guidelines recommend that emergency transfusions of O (RhD) negative RBCs should be administered as quickly as possible when a patient's blood type is unknown or when there is an immediate need for transfusion to prevent serious outcomes. The guidelines emphasize the importance of Timely administration to avoid complications and to optimize patient outcomes. NHSBT guidelines support the NICE recommendations, emphasising that O (RhD) negative RBCs should be provided promptly in emergency situations. The guidelines also outline the importance of efficient blood inventory management to minimize wastage and ensure that blood products are used within their optimal timeframe.

The audit results indicated that 70% of the issued O (RhD) negative RBCs were transfused. Of these, 85% of transfusions were documented as compliant with the recommended emergency use guidelines. This suggests that a substantial majority of transfusions adhered to the NICE and NHSBT recommendations for urgent administration. However 20% returned unused and 10% expired. The root causes for these issues were identified as: on wastage, the high percentage of returned units (20%) suggests that in some cases, O (RhD) negative RBCs were issued prematurely before confirming the patient's blood type. This could be related to delays in clinical decision-making or inefficiencies in the blood issuing process.

The 10% of units that expired point to potential issues with the management of blood inventory. Units that are not used within their optimal timeframe are at risk of becoming expired, leading to wastage. The audit data reveals that while the majority of transfusions were conducted in compliance with emergency protocols, there were cases where delays occurred. Administrative delays in transfusion or confirmation of blood type contributed to the expiration of units. This underscores the need for improved co-ordination between clinical teams and the blood bank to ensure Timely administration of emergency O (RhD) negative RBCs.

This high compliance rate is encouraging and suggests that clinical staff are generally adhering to best practices for emergency transfusions. Consistent adherence to guidelines is critical in ensuring that emergency transfusions are appropriately managed, thereby minimizing the risk of haemolytic reactions and other adverse events [3]. However, the 10% of non-compliant cases, primarily due to known blood types and elective procedures, highlight areas where practices may need to be reviewed and reinforced. Education and regular audits could help address these gaps, ensuring that guidelines are followed more strictly across all scenarios.

The audit identified 20% of units being returned unused and 10% expired. These figures are notably high compared to industry standards, where the acceptable wastage rate is generally below 10% [1]. This level of wastage represents a considerable concern, both in terms of financial cost and resource availability. The expiration of 73 units (10%) points to the complexity in the transfusion and blood management process. The primary cause of expiration was identified as administrative delays, where the time taken to decide on transfusion or to transport the units to the point of care exceeded the shelf life of the RBCs. The return of 146 units (20%) unused is another significant concern. These units were issued in anticipation of need, often during emergency scenarios where it was difficult to predict the exact blood requirements. The fact that such a large proportion of units were returned suggests that there may be a tendency to over-issue RBCs in high-pressure situations. While it is understandable that clinicians would prefer to err on the side of caution, the high return rate indicates a need for improved predictive tools and protocols that can estimate the number of units required in various emergency scenarios.

The root causes of wastage included returned units due to blood type confirmation and expired units due to administrative delays. Addressing these issues is crucial for improving efficiency and reducing costs. Strategies to mitigate wastage could include forecasting and inventory management, more rigorous pre-transfusion testing, and enhanced communication between clinical teams to prevent over-ordering [4].

Excess stock was associated with higher wastage, which points to potential issues in inventory forecasting and management. Although, the demand for O-negative blood can be highly unpredictable. In emergencies, such as major trauma incidents, surgeries, or massive transfusions, there may be a sudden and significant need for O-negative blood, which is universally compatible with all patients. Keeping excess stock ensures that the hospital can meet this demand without delay. However, effective stock management is critical in balancing supply and demand for emergency blood products. Overstocking can lead to increased wastage, particularly if units are not used before their expiry. A dynamic inventory management system that adjusts stock levels based on real-time data and usage patterns could help reduce excess and ensure that supply aligns with demand more accurately [5]. Improving documentation practices through better training and auditing can enhance the overall quality of transfusion services [6].

Comparing the results of this audit with those from similar studies and guidelines highlights both strengths and areas for improvement. Studies have shown that while compliance with transfusion guidelines is generally high, wastage rates can vary significantly depending on the practices and systems in place [7]. This audit's findings are consistent with the literature, which emphasizes the importance of optimizing stock management and reducing wastage to improve overall efficiency and resource utilisation.

Although compliance with guidelines is generally high, the significant wastage and stock management issues identified highlight areas for improvement. Addressing these issues through enhanced training, better inventory management. Continuous monitoring and regular audits will support ongoing improvements and ensure that best practices are maintained.

Limitations

While the clinical audit on the usage and wastage of emergency O (RhD) negative red blood cells (RBCs) provides valuable insights, several limitations must be acknowledged to fully understand the scope and applicability of the findings. These limitations can affect the interpretation of the results and the subsequent recommendations.

The audit data was collected from a single blood bank and hospital setting. Findings may not be generalizable to other institutions with different patient demographics. Variations in blood bank operations and clinical procedures could result in different outcomes. The audit focused on emergency transfusions, which may not fully reflect the broader usage patterns of O (RhD) negative RBCs in non-emergency situations.

The audit covered a 12-month period, which may not capture long-term trends in RBC usage and wastage. A longer time frame might provide a more comprehensive view of patterns and help identify trends over time. The audit was retrospective, relying on historical data. This approach limits the ability to address real-time issues or implement immediate interventions during the data collection phase. Prospective audits or real-time monitoring could provide more dynamic insights. The data analysis methods used, such as descriptive statistics and compliance rates, provide a broad overview but may not capture nuanced aspects of practice or patient outcomes.

Conclusion

The audit aimed to evaluate compliance with established guidelines, assess the extent of wastage, and determine the effectiveness of emergency blood transfusions. The audit revealed a high level of adherence to clinical guidelines, with 90% of emergency O (RhD) negative RBC transfusions being compliant with the NICE and NHSBT recommendations. This indicates that most transfusions were conducted in line with best practices for urgent administration.

Despite the high compliance rate, the audit uncovered level of wastage, of the issued O (RhD) negative RBC units. The wastage was primarily due to two factors which are unused returns and expiration. 20% of the units were returned unused to the blood bank. This suggests complexities in the transfusion process of ordering and issuing blood, where units were requested but not transfused, administrative delays leading to the expiration of units. Addressing these issues is crucial to reducing wastage.

The average inventory turnover rate was 3.5, indicating that blood stocks were reasonably aligned with usage patterns. However, higher stock levels were associated with increased wastage, suggesting the need for more precise inventory management. The data points to a need for improved stock management practices to prevent overstocking and understocking. Enhanced inventory tracking and predictive analytics could help in aligning supply with demand more accurately.

Conducting additional audits and studies to explore long-term trends, investigate the root causes of wastage in more detail, and evaluate the impact of implemented changes on both blood management practices and patient outcomes.

In summary, this audit has provided valuable insights into the use and wastage of emergency O (RhD) negative RBCs, highlighting both strengths and areas for improvement. While compliance with guidelines is generally high and patient outcomes are positive, significant wastage and administrative delays represent key

challenges that need to be addressed. Implementing the recommendations and addressing the identified limitations, healthcare providers can enhance blood transfusion practices, reduce wastage, and ultimately improve patient care.

Future audits should focus on the implementation and effectiveness of the recommended changes, such as improving inventory management systems, refining blood ordering processes, and providing targeted training for staff. Additionally, expanding the scope of audits to include multiple institutions could provide further insights into common challenges and best practices across different healthcare settings.

Implementing real-time monitoring systems to track blood usage and wastage dynamically by utilising technology such as RFID tracking or real-time data analytics platforms to monitor blood inventory and usage in real-time, allowing for immediate intervention when issues arise.

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